

Agroforestry agrifood and market resilience

- Fostering specific land management should be linked to an economic return associated with environmental care and social acceptance.
- Multiple products are delivered by agroforestry management land, interconnecting different value chains
- The AF4EU agroforestry value chains analysis identified 12 value chains across Europe well interconnected with the media and people.

Agroforestry value chains connectivity

AF4EU identified 12 main agroforestry value chain patterns across Europe thanks to the work carried out by over 500 stakeholders across Europe. Identified agroforestry value chains included some specific ones such as aromatic plants, beef livestock, berries, goat, honey, fungi, nuts, wine, while others are more generally implemented such as agritourism (included by actors in all defined value chains) or silvopasture (Figure 1). Moreover, agroforestry value chains are mostly developed in Mediterranean areas followed by the Atlantic areas with scarce presence in the Boreal or Continental European biogeographic regions. These results show that agroforestry fits in different environments.

FIGURE 1. Agroforestry value chains in Europe

Agroforestry value chains interconnections

Agroforestry can be considered a multi-layer value chain system as most of the value chains showed a high degree of connectivity as shown in Figure 2. Agroforestry can also be associated to the concept of the ecointensification of the land linked to the optimization of the use of the resources (upstream) and sell of products (downstream).

FIGURE 2. AF4EU value chain interconnections

The multiple resources use shows a clear connection with the territory use that provides raw material and with the diversification of the products obtained from the same unit of land, diversifying the downstream activities and products. The multiple layer value chain can be perceived as a form of improving socio-economic and environmental connectivity in the territory usually linked to communal areas and cooperatives.

CAP value chains promotion

The current CAP mostly promotes agroecosystem land management as a way to foster sustainable land management without a direct consideration of the whole territory where the land is established and the connections that the specific land, farm and the territory has with the value chains and therefore with the main resources and outcomes produced in the territory. Besides adequate land management, the CAP should deploy better tools considering the connection of the social and the productive and environment CAP objectives. Fostering payments that account high diversification of

the outcomes from the land should be considered and not exclusively taken. For example, payments increase of around 20% when both livestock and permanent products are provided from the same unit of land should be established enhancing economic returns, downstream sectors involvement, territory activities, environmental care while increasing resilience against climate change and markets

MAIN CONCLUSIONS

- **Agroforestry value chains have a rich downstream and upstream diversified set of activities well connected with the territory**
- **Agroforestry value chain can be defined as an interconnected system of specific value chains, where agrotourism is key connecting urban-rural areas.**
- **CAP should develop adequate business environment to promote cooperativism and agroforestry value chains development if territory linked business models associated with short value chains aims at being enhanced.**

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AF4EU: a groundbreaking initiative to foster European agroforestry

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